

Confronting Authoritarianism at Home and Abroad: Academic Freedom in the Shadow of Genocide

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"...if you can't draw the line at genocide, you probably can't draw the line at democracy." (Coates,¹ 2025)

How are we who have studied, researched, and lived in various parts of the MENA region, and who now find our profession, our universities, our colleagues, our students, and perhaps ourselves under attack by the Trump administration, to understand what is happening? While Coates' charge above was not directed at universities, the link he draws between protesting genocide and defending democracy is central to any discussion of academic freedom in the US today. We are involved in a struggle against anti-democratic forces that seek not only to silence the many voices from both inside and outside universities protesting the genocide in Gaza, but also, simultaneously, to impose a broad authoritarian project of white Christian nationalism on the United States (Heritage Foundation 2023). Making sense of this moment is impossible without a recognition of how these two goals are inextricably linked.

¹ The remarks were made in reference to the Democratic party's support for, or failure to recognize, the genocide.

Setting the Stage

For members of our community of scholars who come from authoritarian states, the current script must feel dreadfully familiar. Many of the rest of us, however, having learned what it is like to live under authoritarian regimes as part of our research on the region, with all that means for the protection of sources, colleagues, data, and the circumscribing of some of the most basic elements of academic freedom, are only now being introduced to what it means to experience state repression at home. The fascist policies (Stanley 2018) of this new administration affect how we live our professional lives not only as teachers and scholars, but also as moral citizens; today's threats are both qualitatively different and worse than threats that have arisen under any previous administration (Schrecker 2025).

As political scientists we should be pondering the forces – economic, political, and social – that lead a democracy with a particularly strong tradition of free speech to turn with such destructive vengeance against the cen-

ters of research and knowledge production that have been foundational to its past political, economic, and military strength. The United States today is often described as experiencing “democratic backsliding” or creeping fascism. Yet, given the extensive territorial, political, and economic reach of the US, we should perhaps instead characterize the current period as one of imperial rot, in which whole groups of people – non-white communities, refugees, migrants, and the homeless here, as well as entire populations in the Global South – are deemed disposable (Fraser 2022). The US empire, increasingly hollowed out internally by rising income inequality, outrageous outlays for illegal interventions abroad, and increasingly militarized policing at home, is trampling the rule of law and purging scientific and technocratic expertise. Championing this destruction is the most incompetent, kleptocratic, and unapologetically vicious leadership in our history, intent upon policies that, far from making America great, are in fact hastening institutional collapse and corrosion from within.²

Academic Freedom and Middle East Studies

The defense of universities as centers of critical inquiry has long been a concern of the scholarly community in the US. The 1940 American Association of University Professors (AAUP) “Statement of Principles on Academic Freedom and Tenure and its amendments” (AAUP, n.d.) continues to serve as a foundational document on academic freedom. However, given the nature of the US political system, with its Constitution and Bill of Rights, the AAUP statement imagined that the threats to academic freedom would come from *within the universities themselves*. It

did not foresee that the primary threats to academic freedom might someday come directly *from the US government*, the situation in which we find ourselves today (Sarat 2025).

Over the years, the community of MENA region scholars, including both political scientists and those from other disciplines, has periodically been in the crosshairs of actors working to suppress our research and teaching. Most have been non-governmental ones seeking to stifle free speech on the Middle East. Palestine has been the most prominent and contentious issue, although critiques of broader US Middle East policy have also triggered harassment. For example, after 9/11 some of our colleagues were targeted for offering analyses that attempted to place the attacks in historical and political context. In the period that followed, we were treated to legions of spurious charges on Daniel Pipes’ *Campus Watch* website. Somewhat later, the even more insidious – because of its anonymity, and its targeting of not just faculty but also students – *Canary Mission* began its attacks.

While some of these assaults targeted writings and speech that were deemed anti-American, the actual goal was to intimidate and, later, with the advance of internet technology, “dox” scholars and students for any criticism of Israel or support for the Boycott Divestment and Sanctions (BDS) movement. For decades before there was an International Holocaust Remembrance Alliance (IHRA) definition of antisemitism and the subsequent pressures to adopt it (Middle East Studies Association 2021; Stern 2025), the charge of antisemitism for criticizing Israeli policies was threatening precisely because of the historical record of the Holocaust and its resonance in

² Referring solely to the cuts across the US intelligence agencies, former CIA director William Burns termed the purges underway as “great-power suicide” (Burns 2025).

the West. Indeed, the most potentially damning charge against scholars in our field has been that of engaging in antisemitic (often perverted to mean anti-*Israel*), not anti-*American*, speech. Thus, while recent surveys of Middle East Studies scholars have documented self-censorship in the classroom (Lynch and Telhami 2023), faculty have long been careful, even after securing tenure, when it came to writing, teaching, and speaking on Palestine.

The Current Assault

To understand what we are facing today under the Trump administration, it is important to first highlight the confluence of several key factors prior to autumn 2023.

First, anti-Palestinian racism, anti-Arab racism, and Islamophobia have long flourished in the US, on and off college campuses; nevertheless, universities in the US had gradually become the epicenter of Palestine solidarity activism, in particular regarding BDS. The proliferation of chapters of Students for Justice in Palestine and Jewish Voice for Peace is among the most obvious indicators of this development. It was precisely to quash this anti-Zionist activism that a range of actors began to actively lobby to legislate or impose the adoption of the 2016 IHRA definition of antisemitism at the federal (Committee on Academic Freedom 2022), state, and even municipal level, as well as at universities.

Just as important, the congressional inquisitions that pilloried presidents of top universities beginning in fall 2023 (Committee on Academic Freedom 2024) demonstrated an increasing eagerness by the political right to instrumentalize antisemitism – defined primarily as anything pro-Palestinian – as part of their long-standing project to discredit

America's institutions of higher learning as bastions of a liberal elite or “radical left” orthodoxy. For these right-wing officials – many of whom espouse a white Christian nationalist ideology which is antisemitic, but not, importantly, anti-Zionist – the goal has precious little to do with antisemitism, for which there should be zero tolerance. Rather, they seek to silence “radical” academics and the institutions that harbor them because they view them as responsible for teaching critical thinking and promoting opposition to their authoritarian political program.

US foreign policy also helped bring us to the current crisis. Solid backing for Israel has long been a centerpiece of US Middle East policy, including support for repeated Israeli assaults and wars on Gaza since the Palestinian elections of 2006. Yet, not even the greatest booster of the slaughter of Palestinians could have dreamed of the unprecedented level of US military and political support that we have seen for this genocide (Bilmes, Hartung, and Semler 2024). In previous Israeli wars on Gaza, US administrations set a deadline or a number of days, weeks, or corpses after which they would force a cessation of the bloodletting. The Biden administration broke that model, and, after forcing a ceasefire so as not to detract from the new president's first weeks in office, the Trump administration was content to allow Israel to continue the daily bombings and massacres until the president brokered the October 10 ceasefire/prisoner exchange agreement, the future of which, however, remains uncertain at the time of this writing.

The point here is that this policy atmosphere – particularly during the first months of the genocide before increasing numbers of Americans began to awaken to the butchery and devastation wrought with their tax dol-

lars – had a terrible impact on campuses.

First, it further exacerbated the long-standing power imbalance in the “public sphere” between pro-Israel and Palestine solidarity activism. Then, as the war quickly morphed into a genocide, increasingly widespread and vocal campus anti-genocide activism emerged and, for the first time, growing numbers of university administrations – in some cases of their own volition, in others, pressured by pro-Israel members of the campus communities, outside organizations with a pro-Israel agenda, and/or state or municipal governments – stepped in to suppress programming and protests, sometimes violently. To find domestic precedents for militarized interventions such as we saw at Columbia or UCLA one would have to go back to the Vietnam war era.

Through the end of the Biden administration there were some, largely performative, attempts to address Islamophobia in the US (The White House 2024), in addition to a much broader push to crack down on anything genocide-deniers called antisemitism.³ At the same time, university administrators and local officials, using the traditional charges of antisemitism or support for terrorism, engaged in a range of actions to criminalize and silence those whose research, teaching, scholarship, or activism sought to focus attention on Gaza.

The Authoritarian Turn

What is different since January 2025 is that

the right-wing Trump administration, allied with many of the same pro-Israel forces that sought to suppress Palestine scholarship and activism under Biden, already had a plan in place for a broad-based, frontal attack on education, science, and academic expertise when it came into office. The charge of antisemitism was simply the first battering ram⁴ to be used – in conjunction with a direct assault on any policies, scholarship, or teaching related to diversity, equity, and inclusion, or “DEI” (Chronicle Staff 2025a). The manual for implementing this program is *Project Esther* (National Task Force to Combat Antisemitism 2024). While framed as targeting antisemitism, *Project Esther* takes aim only at those individuals and groups who are critical of Israel, ignoring the antisemitism inherent in the white Christian nationalism that animates many members of the Trump administration and its supporters. Its program seeks to suppress protest and free speech on campus by targeting faculty and staff, destroying student activist groups, and militarizing campuses. Its goal is to intimidate members of campus communities and beyond to fear for their jobs, visas, and degrees through punishing and criminalizing pro-Palestine advocacy. Its larger project is to silence any communities or movements seeking to protect civil, political, and economic rights, as it destroys centers of critical inquiry in its quest to impose its anti-democratic program.

As the months have passed, we have seen the assault on the universities take myriad devastating forms, in virtually all cases using as

³ The politically motivated and analytically inappropriate pairing of Islamophobia and antisemitism is a topic for another discussion.

⁴ According to a University of Rochester poll conducted in collaboration with UC Berkeley, while 72% of Jewish Americans are concerned about antisemitism on campus, nearly 60% disapprove of the Trump administration’s withholding of federal funding as a means of addressing the issue (Druckman and Fuller 2025). Similarly, many Jewish scholars across the country have rejected the Trump administration’s policy of weaponizing antisemitism. See, for example, Berman, Rosenblatt, and Stahl (2025).

justification spurious charges of rampant antisemitism or insufficient suppression of DEI (Chronicle Staff 2025a). To name some of the most egregious⁵: the sequestering of already appropriated funding for research; the suspension or removal of funding for exchange programs; the imposition of huge fines for purported Title VI violations without benefit of due process; the cancellation of some 6,000 student visas along with multiple cases of brutal arrest, abduction, and detention of anti-genocide activists; the forced resignations of university presidents; threats (as in the case of Harvard) to deny the university the right to seek visas for foreign students; the imposition of a visa ban on a number of African, Middle Eastern, and Asian countries; demands for changes in faculty and student disciplinary processes, admissions criteria, and faculty governance, with the fate of Columbia's Middle East, South Asia and Africa Studies Department the highest-profile example; demands (in the case of UC Berkeley), that the university hand over to the Department of Education the names of faculty, staff, and students who had been accused of involvement in antisemitic incidents; and the replacement of peer review with politicized processes for approving federal grants.

Comparing contexts

Given the increase in gross academic freedom violations we are now witnessing across the US, it is worth reflecting on what attacks on the academy in the MENA region have looked like in comparison. Certainly, control over universities – what they teach, who teaches, who studies there, what research is allowed, and who exercises direct administrative control – has historically been of keen concern to the region's authoritarian regimes.

⁵ For a detailed presentation of the Trump administration's many and various attacks on US universities see Chronicle Staff (2025b).

Among the violations we have become accustomed to seeing are: state interference in the appointment of university faculty, administrators, and leadership; state restrictions on courses of study offered, course materials used, and topics taught; state security force involvement on and near campuses to prevent protests; surveillance and censorship of faculty and students in the classroom, in campus activities, on social media, and in extra-mural speaking and writing; little or no faculty input into university administration and governance; limits on what can be researched and published; restrictions on conference travel and content of participation; interference in university acceptance based on ideological, ethnic, or religious grounds; and dismissal or imprisonment of those who challenge these forms of control. Sadly, we are now witnessing a proliferation of many of these same violations in the US. Indeed, in discussions of creeping authoritarianism, some have drawn parallels between what is happening today in the US and developments in post-2005 Turkey.

That said, we have not (yet) reached fully institutionalized authoritarianism, with the kind of brutality against academics that the Middle East Studies Association (MESA)'s Committee on Academic Freedom has repeatedly written about in Egypt, Iran, Turkey, Bahrain, the UAE and Saudi Arabia. Likewise, though we have seen the increasing securitization of some of our campuses, it pales in comparison to the Israeli occupation's violence in the West Bank, its military assaults against universities, its administrative detention of faculty and students, and its military checkpoints' impairing of physical access to campuses, now against the backdrop of a growing campaign of ethnic cleansing.

Worse, in Sudan – where, on January 7, 2025 the US declared the on-going killing a genocide – Libya, Yemen, Lebanon, Syria, and Iraq, repeated military invasions, attacks, and internal conflicts have taken the lives of tens, hundreds, or thousands of students and faculty in addition to destroying the physical infrastructure and research resources of higher education institutions. And then there is Gaza where, despite the findings of a growing chorus of outraged UN, international human rights, humanitarian relief, legal, and scholarly organizations, the US continues to refuse to declare a genocide, and where the scholasticide (Moody 2025) is an imponderable nightmare.

Navigating the current crisis

In the US, in situations of rights violations, we are accustomed to appealing to established processes, the courts, and the rule of law, although university offices charged with conducting Title VI and Title IX complaints rarely receive high marks. Now, however, the Trump administration has gutted the Department of Education’s Civil Rights Division, while changing the focus of what remains to pursuing charges of antisemitism and violations of its abolition of DEI programs. Moreover, the approach of the Department of Education is now “due process be damned”: accuse first, then strive to break the institution by forcing a settlement in line with the Trump administration’s ideological and financial preferences.⁶

How should we understand the concept of responsibility for protecting academic freedom in this context? First, as I hope this essay has made clear, perhaps the greatest error we

can commit is to (re)act in a way that fails to appreciate that what is being violated goes far beyond our cherished right to study and teach what we choose. As political scientists who study authoritarian regimes, we are particularly well-placed to – and we should – call out the similarities between what we have studied and experienced in the MENA region, and what is happening here in the US. Indeed, we have a special responsibility to explain to others how the administration’s serial attempts at extortion and its flagrant violations of university autonomy are but one part of a multi-pronged attack on American democracy – however deeply flawed – itself.

Administrators, in their eagerness to spare themselves the Trump administration’s wrath and demonstrate their zeal to follow federal or state policies of repression, have often chosen to target the most vulnerable: junior, un- or non-tenured, non-citizen faculty and students, frequently women and men of color. Hence, those of us who are the least vulnerable – senior, tenured, “white,” citizens – have an outsized responsibility to take the lead in demanding respect for academic freedom, speaking out against administrators who prefer conciliation with fascism to fighting it, and defending less well-positioned faculty as well as students. At the same time, as scholars of the region most immediately in the administration’s sights, we have a duty to continue doing what we do: insist upon sovereignty over what we teach in our classes, engage in quality academic programming in our areas of expertise, and provide informed commentary on the myriad threats we face. And in all cases, continue teaching and talking about Palestine.

⁶ The American Council on Education has a website that tracks Trump administration executive orders and actions impacting the Department of Education and higher education more broadly. See American Council on Education (2025).

Upholding or fighting for academic freedom was never just an individual matter.

Now more than ever it is about community and coalitions, both on and off campus. Seek out allies among your colleagues for solidarity and collective action; join your campus branch of AAUP, which has filed numerous lawsuits against the Trump administration and is engaging in broad mobilization across the US; become a member of MESA, if you are not already, as it has taken a leading role in advocacy for our Middle East Studies community and for free speech more broadly.⁷ Most important, do not obey in advance (Snyder 2025) and do not surrender. When you defend your students, you defend all students; when you speak up for a colleague, you defend all our colleagues; and when you insist on your right to teach what you know is most appropriate, you defend all of our rights to do so. Each time you speak out for freedom, whether of expression, for the academy, or from growing authoritarianism at home, you are doing so for all the rest of us, in what is surely the most consequential fight of our lives. ♦

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⁷ On September 30, Judge William G. Young of the U.S. District Court for the District of Massachusetts ruled in a lawsuit filed by MESA, AAUP, and others, that the Trump administration's policy of arresting, detaining and deporting noncitizen students and faculty for their pro-Palestinian advocacy violated the First Amendment. See "Judge Rules on Lawsuit Regarding First Amendment Rights" (2025).

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